

Assessment of an Optimistic Bias in Social Media Messages

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ABSTRACT

Consistent with psychological theory and research, in the present study we demonstrate that people display a generic optimistic bias by showing more positive sentiment in social media messages about the future rather than the past. In addition, we outline a method for evaluating the validity of the commercial monitoring tool used for the automated sentiment analysis, thereby assessing the usefulness of such a tool in web-based research into human behavior.

1 INTRODUCTION

The web provides valuable data to investigate social, economic, or psychological phenomena that would otherwise be hard to study on a large scale [1]. The main goal of the current work is to investigate whether people, consistent with psychological theory, display a generic optimistic bias by showing more positive sentiment in social media messages with temporal references to the future compared to the past.

To assess this bias, we use a commercial web monitoring tool providing automated sentiment analysis. An important additional goal is to verify the validity of this analysis. Indeed, since commercial tools have enabled the use of automated sentiment analysis by social science researchers with a non-technical background, it is of crucial importance to verify if such tools give usable and valid answers to their research questions. In order to know whether the outcome of an analysis can be trusted, we need to verify whether the tool introduces systematic errors that interfere with our research question. For example, a supervised machine learning system might assign importance to certain

words that are actually irrelevant or it might incorrectly interpret certain words as positive/negative due to their overrepresentation in a certain class in the training data. What is especially important in the context of the present study is the possibility that the system might interpret the very subject of the query (i.e., temporal references to the future or the past) as a feature indicating positive or negative sentiment. It is therefore important to test the validity of the commercial monitoring tool used for the automated sentiment analysis, thereby investigating the usefulness of such a tool in web-based research into human behavior.

2 BACKGROUND

2.1 Generic optimistic bias

Looking back on the past and imagining the future make use of similar cognitive and neural mechanisms [2], but imagining future events is more difficult than recalling the past. When people imagine their future, they have to draw on elements of the past and reconstruct them into possible future scenarios, but the imagination of the future is not a complete reflection of the past. Psychological studies demonstrate that individuals' thoughts about the future are often more positive than memories of the past [3], suggesting that people tend to envision outcomes that are in line with their needs while imagining the future [4, 5].

This "optimistic bias" can be explained by temporal self-appraisal theory [6] and temporal construal theory [7]. Temporal self-appraisal theory states that we want to see ourselves as improving upon who we were in the past [6]. To this end, we may go as far as to derogate our past selves to maintain a positive self-view, and to conclude that we are improving, even when there is

no actual improvement [3, 4, 6]. Temporal construal theory posits that the more distant events are, the more abstract they become [2, 4]. That is, people base their representations of distant future events on more abstract features, whereas they focus on more concrete features for near future events [7]. A focus on abstract features tends to promote envisioning optimal outcomes [5].

Several studies have observed that people are more positive about the future than about the past when they are instructed to write about past or imagined future events, or to rate the probability of experiencing specific events [2, 3, 8, 9]. Moreover, people also tend to believe their futures will be more positive than their acquaintances' [2, 4, 6, 9]. However, none of these studies have tested whether such an optimistic bias also occurs outside of the lab. For example, in a more naturalistic (social media) setting.

2.2 The validity of the sentiment analysis

Sentiment analysis on social media content is usually performed using a lexicon-based approach, (supervised) machine learning, or a combination of the two [10]. Lexicon-based approaches leverage lists of words previously annotated as positive or negative in order to determine the overall sentiment score for the message, while machine learning approaches typically involve training a classifier on a number of features selected from the messages previously labeled as positive or negative. In both cases, when using automated sentiment analysis in web-based studies, the words that are the subject of a query in researching a particular question can be interpreted as either positive or negative by the classifier, which will invalidate the results of the research. Therefore, the results obtained by automated sentiment analysis need to be validated.

3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Selection of public social media messages

We used a social media monitoring service to collect a sample of 3.5 million publicly available social media messages, published from 2009 until the end of 2017. To obtain diverse messages that were written about the past and future, we used different queries containing temporal references varying in time lag. All messages were automatically classified as negative, neutral or positive.

3.2 Analyzing social media messages

Average sentiment scores of future- vs. past-related social media messages were compared within (monthly) time frames, and for different time lags, amounting to a total of 535 tests of our main hypothesis.

Verification of the sentiment tool is currently ongoing. We analyzed the relative frequency distributions of temporal expressions across the positive, negative and neutral classes, as well as the most frequent words across all classes, in order to gain insight into the internal functioning of the tool. The next step is to run an independent sentiment analysis on a subset of the data. We also created an evaluation set of 22,000 messages. We are using crowdsourcing for annotating the messages with gold labels in order to compare them with the scores obtained from the tool.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

According to the sentiment scores obtained from the social media monitoring service and the calculated effect sizes, 474 of our 535 tests (90.8%) confirmed that social media messages referring to the future are more positive than messages referring to the past. In addition, our analyses showed that the effect was more consistent and generally stronger for messages referring to more distant time frames. It is important to note that these findings were obtained with social media messages that were written in a naturalistic context, without instructing users to write about or consciously appraise past and future events, thereby showing that an optimistic bias occurs in natural language, and in daily human behavior. Further establishing the consistency and size of these effects will help to assess human biases in reflecting on past and future events. This may have practical implications especially in situations when unbiased estimates are key, such as in financial forecasting, organizational planning, or policy making.

The validation of the used sentiment analysis tool is currently being conducted and the latest results will be presented at the conference. However, additional research is needed to give more insight into possible limitations of commercial sentiment analyzers. We believe this project is a first step towards developing a systematic method for testing the bias in such tools.

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